

A FATIGUE STUDY AND AN INVESTIGATION ON MECHANICALLY FASTENED JOINTS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF A FLAP.

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Two studies which were carried out in behalf of the development of a schematic flap are treated:

- a study on the behaviour of carbon-epoxy laminates consisting of layers in the 0° , $+45^{\circ}$ and 90° direction under cyclic multi-axial loading;
- an evaluation of several fastener-types with the aid of the single-lap joints. The most promising fasteners have been tested more thoroughly with the aid of a test set-up in which the characteristic joint in the flap (a row of fasteners loaded in shear) could be tested.

As the tests were carried out in support of the development of the flap, they are of a somewhat ad-hoc nature. However, some general trends can be indicated, so that a more basic test programme can be defined.

This research program was partly sponsored by the Netherlands Agency for Aerospace Programs (NIVR).

1 INTRODUCTION

During the past decade a number of aircraft components have been developed at Fokkers in modern fibre reinforced plastics to demonstrate the viability of using these materials for civil aircraft. This work was done in collaboration with the National Aerospace Laboratory NLR and the Delft University of Technology. The components developed and produced until now are: F28-nosewheeldoors, the F28-speedbrake, a schematic F28-speedbrake, the A300-main undercarriage leg fairing and a schematic flap for an F28-successor. This work was supported by a large number of research studies. In this paper two studies will be treated which were carried out on behalf of the schematic flap, viz. a fatigue study of ca-ep laminates and an investigation into mechanically fastened joints. As all the tests reported in this paper were carried out in support of the flap programme, it will be appreciated that they are of a somewhat ad-hoc nature and so will not all be of general application.

The cross-section of the flap is given in fig. 1; a detailed description is given in [1]. As the flap is loaded in bending and torsion, the ca-ep faces of the upper and lower honeycomb panels are built up of layers in the 0° , $+45^\circ$ and 90° directions. Loading of such a fibre controlled laminate results in sites of matrix damage long before ultimate laminate failure due to fibre failure. Due to the high daily load on the flap (daily load ≈ 0.6 design ultimate load), it was expected that the laminate would be fatigue sensitive because the cyclic loading gives rise to a degradation of the matrix and so a decrease of the strength of the layers could be expected because of the worse support of the fibres. The tests to investigate this problem will be treated in section 2.

Fig. 1 Cross-section of the schematic flap.

The lower panel of the flap is attached to the spars by means of mechanical fasteners. The row of fasteners is loaded in shear due to the torsion loading on the flap. In the vicinity of the heaviest loaded rib protruding head bolts can be used, while for the remainder only blind fasteners with flush head can be used. Little information is available on the behaviour of blind fasteners in all carbon-epoxy constructions. Webb [2] gives some design figures for Avdel-rivets in all ca-ep constructions; as the ca-ep thickness in that study is insufficient to accommodate the rivet head, the thickness is increased with packing material. However, the laminate thickness in the joint of the flap is sufficient to accommodate the rivet head ($t \approx 2.5$ mm). Therefore, it was judged appropriate to investigate whether it is possible to use blind bolts in the laminate of the joint without packings. The behaviour of some types of blind bolts has been compared with the aid of single-lap joint test specimens; the results will be treated in section 3. Although only a few tests have been performed, it was possible to select a fastener type for the flap, while further a better insight is obtained in the behaviour of mechanical fasteners in ca-ep, so that a more basic test program can be defined. The most promising fasteners have subsequently been tested more thoroughly with the aid of a test set-up, by means of which the characteristic joint in the flap (a row of fasteners loaded in shear) could be tested.

The carbon-epoxy used in all this work was manufactured from Fothergill and Harvey Code 92 pre-preg tape (T300 - Shell DX 231/DX 137). The fibre volume fraction of the cured laminates is 60%; the thickness of a cured ply is .21 mm.

2 A FATIGUE STUDY FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF THE FLAP

2.1 Introduction

In the literature on composite materials, much attention has been paid to the fatigue behaviour of uni-axial loaded laminates. These studies (see for instance [3], [4] and [5]) show that the fatigue behaviour of composites is governed by the nucleation and growth of sites of local matrix damage in the whole volume of the material during the whole fatigue life-time. Initially such a matrix degradation will not lead to failure of a fibre controlled laminate, because the load is carried over by the fibres. However, the continuing growth of matrix damage in and between the plies, will finally lead to a worse support of the fibres; finally fibre failure will occur in a ply so that laminate failure is introduced.

In [4] and [5] results are given of uni-axial tensile fatigue tests on ca-ep and gl-ep laminates consisting of layers in the 0° and 90° direction (cross-ply laminates). It appeared that these laminates exhibit proportional limit knees on their static tensile stress-strain curves when they are loaded in a principal material direction; the laminates are damaged significantly by applied stress levels that exceed this value. Cycling tensile loading at a stress level below the proportional limit, does not lead to failure of the cross-ply laminate after 10^7 cycles. However, cycling tensile fatigue loading at stress levels that exceed the proportional limit may lead to fatigue failure or to a low residual tensile strength. Apparently the growth of matrix damage due to the fatigue loading results in a worse support of the fibres.

The ca-ep laminate of the flap is loaded by a multi-axial plane stress state. The stress level at which in static loading first matrix damage will occur can be predicted by determining with the aid of the classical lamination theory the stress state in each layer and by applying per layer a failure criterion in which a distinction is made between fibre failure and matrix failure. For ca-ep Puck's modified failure criterion has proven to be useful (see [6]). If the stress state of a unidirectional layer is defined by the stress vector $\vec{\sigma}_{UD} = \{\sigma_1, \sigma_2, \tau_{12}\}$ with respect to the principal material directions, then failure is predicted if:

$$\sigma_1 \geq \sigma_{1F}^t \quad \text{or} \quad \sigma_1 \leq -\sigma_{1F}^c \quad (1^a)$$

$$\text{or} \quad \frac{\sigma_2^2}{\sigma_{2F}^t \sigma_{2F}^c} + \sigma_2 \left\{ \frac{1}{\sigma_{2F}^t} - \frac{1}{\sigma_{2F}^c} \right\} + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12F}} \right)^2 \geq 1. \quad (1^b)$$

(F: failure; t: tensile; c: compression; σ_{1F}^t etc: uni-axial strength values)

The failure surface defined by these equations is given in fig. 2. If one of the inequalities (1^a) is true, then fibre failure will occur and in the case of inequality (1^b) matrix failure is predicted. So, matrix failure is assumed to be caused only by $\vec{\sigma}_M = \{\sigma_2, \tau_{12}\}$. The reserve factor with respect to matrix failure can now be calculated for each ply of a laminate by:

$$\text{RFM} = \frac{\left| \vec{\sigma}_{MF} \right|}{\left| \vec{\sigma}_M \right|} = \frac{\sigma_2 \left\{ \frac{1}{\sigma_{2F}^c} - \frac{1}{\sigma_{2F}^t} \right\} + \sqrt{\sigma_2^2 \left\{ \frac{1}{\sigma_{2F}^t} + \frac{1}{\sigma_{2F}^c} \right\}^2 + 4 \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12F}} \right)^2}}{2 \left\{ \frac{\sigma_2}{\sigma_{2F}^t \sigma_{2F}^c} + \left(\frac{\tau_{12}}{\tau_{12F}} \right)^2 \right\}} \quad (2)$$

If $\text{RFM} \leq 1$, then matrix failure will occur. The RFM of a laminate is the lowest value of the RFM's which have been calculated for the constituent plies. If $\text{RFM} \leq 1$ then matrix failure is predicted in the laminate; ultimate laminate failure is predicted if inequality (1^a) is true for one of the plies.

Fig. 2 Failure surface according to Puck's modified failure criterion.

The RFM of a laminate which has been determined in this way, will generally be conservative due to the non-linear $\tau_{12} - \gamma_{12}$ behaviour. Another reason is that in Puck's criterion uni-axial ply strength values are used. This is correct for uni-directional laminates. However, in multidirectional laminates often crack constraint does occur at small ply thicknesses (see [7]).

In a preliminary analysis of the flap, RFM ≈ 1.6 was found to be the lowest reserve factor with respect to matrix failure of the laminates at daily load. However, in a calculation in which the curing stresses (due to $\Delta T = 100^\circ\text{C}$) were also considered, a much lower value was found: RFM* = .85. In these calculations mean uni-axial strength values were used in the failure criterion. This RFM was found for a ply in the 45° -direction; the multiaxial stress state of that ply is given in fig. 3. The RFM's of the adjacent plies are higher. So, matrix failure may occur in the laminate of the flap at load levels below daily load. However, by application of Puck's failure criterion for fibre failure in the plies, it was demonstrated that in static loading no laminate failure will occur up to design ultimate load (= 1.67 * daily load); in these calculations A-values were used for the uni-directional strengths in fibre direction.

Fig. 3. Stress state in laminate with the lowest RFM.

The fatigue problem may now be stated as follows: does cycling at daily load of the laminate of the flap result in a growth of matrix damage and so in a worse support of the fibres? This would lead to a lower laminate strength after cycling or to fatigue failure. It is expected that matrix degradation in a ply will particularly influence the compression strength in fibre direction.

2.2 Test procedure

No simple test method is available to subject a laminate to a cycling multi-axial stress state. However, on account of the formulation of the fatigue problem as given above, a simple test can be defined to obtain a first insight into the fatigue behaviour of the flap-laminate. For that purpose a cross-ply laminate has to be loaded by a cycling uni-axial tensile load in such a way that the RFM* of the ply with the fibres perpendicular to the load direction equals the reserve factor with respect to matrix failure of the laminate of the flap (RFM* = .85); then, the damage which originates in the cross-ply test specimen will be comparable with the matrix damage in the laminate of the flap. After cycling of the test specimen, the reduction in strength due to the matrix-degradation, can be determined by residual strength-tests in the two principal material directions of the cross-ply; particular attention has to be paid to a possible reduction in compression strength due to matrix damage. Because of the similarity of the matrix damage in the test specimen and in the laminate of the flap, it is expected that in the case of the flap a similar strength reduction due to cyclic loading has to be accounted for.

In the determination of the cycling load level of the crossplied test specimen, the cure stresses have to be accounted for. However, the cure stresses σ_2 and τ_{12} in the plies of the cross-ply are nearly as great as the cure stresses in a laminate consisting of plies in 0° , $+45^\circ$ and 90° direction. For this reason, the uni-axial load on the cross-ply can be chosen in such a way that the RFM due to the load only, corresponds with the RFM due to the daily load on the laminate of the flap; in this way the RFM* (in which the influence of cure stresses is accounted for) of the test specimen is always less than the RFM* of the laminate of the flap.

As it was found for the flap that RFM = 1.6, the uni-axial load on the cross-ply laminate has to be chosen such that the stress in the load direction of the ply² with fibres perpendicular to the load direction equals: $\sigma_2 = \sigma_{2F}^c / \text{RFM} = 33 / 1.6 = 21 \text{ N/mm}^2$. As $E_2 = 7200 \text{ N/mm}^2$, the cross-ply laminate has to be loaded in such a way that the maximum strain in load direction equals: $\epsilon_{\max} = 21 / 7200 = 0.0029$. In the tests performed at Fokkers $\epsilon_{\max} = 0.3\%$ was used.

In this way a simple test method has been defined to obtain an insight into the fatigue behaviour of laminates. A disadvantage of this method is that the matrix damage in a ply due to the loading in the fibre direction is neglected. In a sequel to the tests treated in this paper, this aspect will be investigated. Another point to be investigated is whether the matrix damage in the cross-ply laminate due to σ_2 alone is comparable with the matrix damage in a multi-directional laminate with high stresses σ_2 and τ_{12} in one of the plies.

The advantages of the test procedure are the simplicity of the method and the fact that no difficulties occur in testing due to free edge-effects. A likely advantage is that the fatigue behaviour of laminates of different composition can be predicted by testing the cross-ply laminates only.

2.3 Experimental program

A total of 8 tensile fatigue test specimens has been fabricated; the dimensions were $270 \times 100 \times 0.84 \text{ mm}$ (see fig. 4a); the laminate lay-up of 4 test specimens was $(90^\circ/0^\circ)_S$, for the others a laminate lay-up $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_S$ was chosen (0° -direction is the load direction). A cycling uni-axial load is applied to these specimens in a 200 kN-Servotest testing machine; $f = 10 \text{ Hz}$; number of cycles = 500,000; $R = 0.1$; maximum load = 18 kN, which corresponds with a strain of 0.3%. One test specimen was cyclic loaded at a load level such that the maximum strain is 0.35% to investigate the growth of the matrix damage due to higher loads. The damage which occurs was determined after the first 60 cycles and then after every 125,000 cycles by an X-ray method;

a tetrabromoethane opaque additive applied at the damage zones enhanced the flaw image.

After cyclic loading the test specimens are sawed as indicated in fig. 4b. Each pair of specimens is used to fabricate a short sandwich column; the dimensions are given in fig. 4c. Furthermore 4 reference test specimens have been fabricated from the same ca-ep plate that is used to fabricate the tensile fatigue test specimens. The compression strength of the short columns has been determined in an Avery-testing machine; the stiffness of the test specimens was determined from the displacement of the compression stamps.

Fig. 4 (a) tensile test specimen; (b) saw pattern of test specimens after cyclic loading; (c) residual strength test specimens.

2.4 Test results and discussion

In the test specimens cycled at a maximum strain of 0.3%, no matrix damage was found by non destructive testing after 60 load cycles. However, after 125,000 load cycles matrix cracks were found in the plies with fibres perpendicular to the load direction; the crack lengths and the number of cracks increased after further fatigue loading. The number of cracks is not great; the average number of matrix cracks in the plies with fibres perpendicular to the load direction was 1 per cm length of the test specimen. Generally the cracks did not span the whole width of the test specimen. In the plies with the fibres parallel to the load direction no matrix cracks were observed.

One $(90^{\circ}/0^{\circ}/0^{\circ}/90^{\circ})$ test specimen was cycled at a maximum strain of 0.35%. In this test specimen a greater crack density was observed. Cracks in the plies with fibres perpendicular to the load direction were already observed after the first 60 cycles. The crack density increased with an increasing number of cycles. In fig. 5 X-ray photo's are given of a part of the laminate after 125,000 and 500,000 cycles; dark lines represent cracks in the plies. With the aid of other NDI-techniques, it was found that the cracks are equally distributed over the two 90° -plies; an average crack density of 4 per cm length was measured. No matrix cracks were observed in the plies with fibres in the load direction; no interlaminar damage was observed.

Fig. 5. Matrix cracks in a test specimen after 125,000 and 500,000 cycles respectively.

It may be concluded from these results that the proportional limit strain at which matrix damage occurs in static loading, will be a strain between 0.3% and 0.35%. If the maximum strain during cyclic loading is below this limit, the material develops cracks only after about 100,000 cycles; the crack density remains small during further load cycling. If the maximum strain during cycling exceeds the proportional limit, then cracks in the plies perpendicular to the load direction will appear even during the first load cycles; the crack density increases with the number of load cycles.

The residual compressive strength and stiffness of the laminates have been determined with the aid of short sandwich columns. No reduction in compressive stiffness was found due to the matrix damage in the laminates. The results for the compressive strength tests are given in table 1.

 type of preloading:	σ_{XF}	σ_{XF} for a $(90^\circ/0^\circ)_s$ laminate	σ_{XF} for a $(0^\circ/90^\circ)_s$ laminate
no preloading (reference)		437 *) 466	477 *) 448 *)
cyclic tensile loading in 90° -direction (matrix cracks in 0° -plies)		428 451	538 *) 489 472 *)
cyclic tensile loading in 0° -direction (matrix cracks in 90° -plies)		459 **)	407 *)

*) failure in Araldite followed by laminate failure.
 **) material of faces has undergone cyclic tension at 0.35%

Only five test specimens failed due to laminate failure in the undisturbed part. The other test specimens failed due to a combined failure of the laminate and the araldite in the zone of force introduction; this is probably due to a non-parallelism of the end-faces or due to the fact that the forces are not introduced regularly in the laminates by the araldite end-faces. Due to this shortcoming in test method and due to the small number of test results, it is not possible to

quantify the reduction in compressive strength due to the matrix cracks. However, qualitatively it may be concluded that, if any reduction exists, it will be small. Only the compressive strength of the $(0^{\circ}/90^{\circ})_s$ -laminates with matrix cracks in the 90° -plies is considerably lower than the strength of the reference test specimens; most probably this is caused by the shape of the test specimen.

As the stiffness of the cross-ply has not been changed due to the matrix cracks, it may be concluded that the stiffnesses of the constituent plies have not been changed. Then it is possible to deduce from the results of table 1 the compressive strength in fibre direction of a ply in a laminate with matrix cracks. The mean value and the standard deviation of the compressive strengths calculated in this way correspond to the values found with the aid of series of compression tests carried out earlier on unidirectional test specimens without matrix failure. This implies for the analysis of the flap that no reduction has to be introduced in the strength in fibre direction of the plies for laminates if $RFM \geq 1.6$ at daily load.

2.5 Conclusion

Cyclic uni-axial tensile loading of a cross-ply gives rise to matrix cracks in the plies perpendicular to the load direction if RFM due to loading equals 1.6 (number of cycles = 500,000). Assuming that this matrix damage is representative for the matrix damage that occurs due to cyclic multi-axial loading in a laminate consisting of plies in 0° , $+45^{\circ}$ and 90° directions with the same RFM , it may be concluded from the residual strength tests on the cross-ply, that in the analysis of the flap no reduction factors have to be introduced for strength and stiffness if $RFM \geq 1.6$ at daily load.

The above reported tests were carried out in support of the flap programme. A sequel to that investigation which is currently going on, is of a more general application. The reduction in compressive strength of cross-ply laminates which have been cycled at higher loads than in this programme will be determined; in this programme another type of compression test specimen will be used (a Celanese compression test installation will be used), while in addition a greater number of specimens will be tested. Another point that will be investigated is whether the matrix damage in the cross-ply laminate due to σ_2 alone, is comparable with the matrix damage in multi-directional laminates with high stresses σ_2 , τ_{12} and σ_1 in one of the plies.

3 MECHANICALLY FASTENED JOINTS

3.1 Introduction

The thickness of the laminates in the joint area is about 2.5 mm; about 50% of the plies is in 0° -direction and about 50% is in $+45^{\circ}$ -direction (the 0° -direction is the span direction of the flap). According to test results given in [8] and [9] and test results found at Fokkers, the bearing strength is maximum by applying such a laminate composition; small variations in laminate composition do not result in appreciable changes in bearing strength. The diameter of the fasteners is 5 mm; the depth of the countersunk of blind fasteners of this diameter is less than 2.1 mm, so that the cylindrical part of the hole is at least 0.4 mm (for metal plates 0.2 mm is required). A pitch of $4d = 20$ mm was chosen; earlier tests showed that then joint failure is induced by bearing failure.

To prevent corrosion in the joint, the fasteners have to be manufactured from titanium, inonel or CRES, while monel or steel are marginally acceptable. Another restriction to be taken into account in the selection of fasteners is that only low shank expansion fasteners may be used with low tail forming forces. These restrictions effectively narrow the field of fastener types to be used. In table 2 a survey is given of the bolts and blind rivets to be evaluated for application in the flap; some of these rivets require a metal backing plate or a washer under the tail, namely the Bulbed Cherry Lock rivet and the Huck rivet.

The fasteners are compared with the aid of single-lap joints; the results are given in the sections 3.2 and 3.3. The most promising fasteners have been tested more thoroughly with the aid of a test set-up by means of which the characteristic joint in the flap (a row of fasteners loaded in shear) could be tested; these tests are treated in the sections 3.4 and 3.5.

Title	Bolt, close tol.	Bolt, 100°csk.	Jo-bolt, 100°csk.	Visu-lok, 100°csk.
Designation	NAS 673V-5	NAS 333CPA-5	NSA 54204-190-03	PLT170-6-3
d (mm)	4.81	4.81	4.80	5.00
c (mm)	-	2.03	2.0	1.96
nut (rivet)			BS S 103	Ti 6Al-4V
sleeve			BS S 103	Ti 6Al-4V
screw (stem)	Ti 6Al-4V	steel	CRES	CRES
Title	Big-foot, 100°csk.	Huck, 100°csk.	Bulbed Cherry Lock	Bulbed Cherry Lock, 100°csk.
Designation	JLY 1236-6-3	SB 100-T6-4	NAS 1738M6-4	NAS 1739M6-4
d (mm)	5.00	5.00	5.15	5.15
c (mm)	1.96	2.03	-	1.6
nut (rivet)	Ti 6Al-4V	AISI 4027	monel	monel
sleeve	inconel			
screw (stem)	CRES	AISI 4027	inconel	inconel

Table 2. Survey of investigated fasteners.

3.2 The single-lap tests

The test specimen geometry is given in fig. 6. The laminate lay-up is: (+45°/-45°/0°/0°/0°/-45°/+45°/0°/0°/0°/-45°/+45°); thickness = 2.5 mm. A titanium backing-plate is applied for Bulbed Cherry Lock-rivets and for Huck-rivets as indicated in fig. 6. The Ti-strips are bonded on both sides of the specimen for reasons of symmetry; the rivets are countersunk in the ca-ep only.

Fig. 6. Test specimen geometry; detail of metal backing for Bulbed Cherry Lock rivets and Huck rivets.

The test specimens have been loaded in uni-axial tension in an Instron 1272 testing machine. The tests to determine the yield load $P_{2\%}$ at which the permanent set over the joint equals $0.04d = 0.20$ mm, are carried out under load control (2 kN/min); a low loading speed was chosen because of creep in the joint. The tests to determine the ultimate load P_u are carried out under displacement control (0.4 mm/min).

A number of specimens is tested in tensile fatigue in an Instron 1272 testing machine; $R = 0.1$ in all tests. A frequency of 5 Hz was chosen to avoid significant heating effects in the carbon-epoxy. During fatigue testing the change in permanent set of the joint has been recorded.

3.3 Results of single-lap joint tests.

The results of the static tests are given in table 3. In all tests joint failure was due to bearing failure of the ca-ep; at failure the load was practically constant with increasing hole distortion. As generally $P_u > 1.5 P_{2\%}$, the load at which 2% permanent deformation of the holes occurs will be critical for the strength of joints in ca-ep structures with the considered fasteners (the protruding load bolt excluded).

Table 3. Test results static tests.

Test	Load per fastener (N)							
	t joint		1	2	3	4	5	mean
Bolt, close tolerance, hex. head (NAS 673V-5)	4.95	P_u $P_{2\%}$	8580 -	- 6250	8600 7000			8590 6620
Bolt, 100° csk. (NAS 333CPA-5)	4.85	P_u $P_{2\%}$	7240 -	7560 3450	7220 3150			7340 3300
Jo-bolt, 100° csk. (NSA 54204-190-03)	4.90	P_u $P_{2\%}$	5030 3470	- 3450	- 3200	- 2900		5030 3250
Visu-lok, 100° csk. (PLT 170-6-3)	5.0	P_u $P_{2\%}$	4650 -	5150 3200	5290 3250			5030 3230
	4.65	P_u $P_{2\%}$	4400 2250	3950 2850	5350*) 2750			4570 2620
Big-foot, 100° csk. (JLY 1236-6-3)	4.95	P_u $P_{2\%}$	5000 2800					5000 2800
Bulbed Cherry Lock, 100° csk. (NAS1739M6-4)+Ti-strip (1 mm)	5.8	P_u $P_{2\%}$	5030 -	5050 3000	5225 3000	- 3000	- 2750	5100 2940
Huck rivet, 100° csk. (SB 100-T6-4) + Ti-strip (.8 mm)	5.65	P_u	5250	-	-	-		5250
		$P_{2\%}$	2000	2000	1800	1600		1850

*) specimen with Ti-strips

P_u : failure load

$P_{2\%}$: load at which permanent set equals $0.04d = 0.20$ mm.

The result for the torqued bolts with protruding head corresponds with data given in the literature for comparable tests. The high bearing strength is characteristic for torqued bolts; much lower values are obtained for non-torqued bolts. The increase in failure load with clamping load can be attributed to the frictional effect and to the restraining effect of the bolt. (see [8] and [10]). The lateral constraint σ_z of the ca-ep stabilizes the fibre reinforced material in the vicinity of the hole, so that in that region higher compression stresses are possible in fibre direction. A question which arises when torqued bolts are used in ca-ep airplane constructions is, whether the lateral constraint σ_z will not decrease in service due to stress relaxation in the ca-ep, so that the bearing strength diminishes. In a sequel to the tests treated here, this problem will be investigated.

The $P_{2\%}$ for the torqued countersunk bolt is low in comparison with the value found for the protruding head bolt; for the countersunk Jo-bolt and Visu-Lok comparable values were found if the total thickness of the joint is 4.9 ± 5.0 mm. This reduction is due to stress concentrations in the ca-ep plate at the transition of the cylindrical part to the countersunk part of the hole. The reduction in $P_{2\%}$ depends strongly on the height of the cylindrical part of the countersunk hole in one plate. This becomes evident from the results of the tests on the Visu-Loks in the lap-joints of total thickness of 4.65 mm where the height is about 0.2 mm instead of 0.4 mm as in the other test specimens; a great reduction in $P_{2\%}$ was found. Investigation of the individual test results showed that the lower values for $P_{2\%}$ are obtained with test specimens with the smallest height. Apparently it is necessary to require in the inhomogeneous ca-ep a minimum height of the cylindrical part of a countersunk hole greater than usual in metals; the required height will be dependent on the stacking sequence too. In a sequel to the tests treated here, this problem will be investigated.

Comparison of the results for the countersunk bolt, the Jo-bolt and the Visu-Lok shows that $P_{2\%}$ is broadly the same for these fasteners; however, the failure load of the countersunk bolt is considerably greater than the failure load of the other two. Due to the greater contact area between the nut of the bolt and the ca-ep plate, the tilting of the bolt is better prevented. A larger area will also be obtained by application of a metal backing plate under the formed head of the (blind) bolt; in the case of the Visu-Lok with a Ti-strip better results for P_u were obtained. So, it is important that the contact area between the heads of the fastener and the ca-ep is as large as possible. Therefore the Big-foot would be suited to be used in ca-ep. In this test programme only one specimen with this fastener could be investigated. The strength results are comparable with those of the Jo-bolt and the Visu-Lok. These fasteners will be evaluated more thoroughly before long.

The results for P_u and $P_{2\%}$ which are obtained for the Bulbed Cherry Lock rivet with a Ti-backing plate do not differ much from the results obtained for the Jo-bolt. Better results for $P_{2\%}$ were expected because of the smaller flush head. The relatively low $P_{2\%}$ is due to the fact that the small formed head does not prevent the rotation of the tail. This becomes more evident from the test results given in table 4. Application of a protruding head fastener leads only to a relatively small increase in P_u and $P_{2\%}$. So, the mechanical behaviour of the fastener is not defined by the flush head or the protruding head, but by the formed head. The results in table 4 show also that application of a Ti-strip results in a higher P_u ; this is due to the fact that the rivet pull through is prevented by the strip. The tilting of the fastener is not well prevented by the Ti-strip.

Fastener type		P_u [N]	$P_{2\%}$ [N]
protruding head	NAS 1738M6-4	3800	3000
protruding head + Ti-strip (1.0 mm)	NAS 1738M6-4	5640	3250
100° csk. head	NAS 1739M6-4	3490	2500
100° csk. head + Ti-strip (1.0 mm)	NAS 1739M6-4	5100	2940

Table 4. Test results for Bulbed Cherry Lock-rivets.

The load at which 2% permanent hole deformation occurs when Huck-rivets are used is low. The formed head of the Huck-rivet is comparable with the head of the Bulbed Cherry Lock-rivet; however, the flush head is higher. Due to the bad support at the flush head and at the formed head, large hole deformations occur. The fact that the minimum grip length of this fastener equals the thickness of the joint may have contributed to the low $P_{2\%}$ value. So, the lateral constraint in the carbon-epoxy will be small. A question that arises is whether the ranges of grip length of the fasteners which have been defined for metal joints, can also be used for ca-ep joints because of the much lower stiffness in thickness direction. This point has to be investigated more thoroughly.

The results for $P_{2\%}$ are obtained from load controlled tests with a low loading speed (2 kN/min). One test on a joint with flush head Bulbed Cherry Lock-rivets with a Ti-strip was performed at a speed of 70 kN/min; in that case $P_{2\%} = 3400$ N and $P_u = 5150$ N was found. Apparently $P_{2\%}$ depends strongly on the test method.

From the above it appears that generally $P_{2\%}$ is critical for static strength calculations of ca-ep joints with the considered fasteners. Some of the joints have been tested in fatigue to investigate the significance of $P_{2\%}$ for the fatigue behaviour. Four types of fasteners have been tested: the protruding head bolt, the flush head Jo-bolt and the flush head Huck-rivet and Bulbed Cherry Lock rivet; the last two with Ti-backing strips. The geometry of the test specimen is the same as for the static tests. When a specimen did not fail after 10^6 cycles, it was cycled at a higher load level. The test results are given in table 5. All the failures occurred due to fatigue of the metal fastener in the flush head or in the protruding head. In all tests at a load level that caused failure, a considerable tilting of the fasteners was observed.

Fastener type	Specimen no.	No. of load cycles ($\times 10^{-5}$) at given P_{\max} per hole [N]										
		2000	2500	2900	3000	3500	3750	4000	4250	5000	6250	
NAS 673V-5	1							10				→ 1.4
	2									10		→ 2.7
	3											→ 5.0
NSA 54204-190-03	1				10							→ 1.6
	2				10							→ 4.0
	3					10						→ 1.8
NAS 1739M6-4 + Ti-strip (1.0 mm)	1	10										→ 2.2
	2	10										→ 1.2
	3											→ 1.5
	4	10										→ 1.0
	5											→ 0.5
SB 100-T6-4 +Ti-strip (0.8 mm)	1	10										→ 8.5
	2											→ 8.0
	3		10									→ 10 → 5.5

Table 5. Results of fatigue tests on lap-joints; $R = 0.1$; $f = 5$ Hz. If a specimen did not fail after 10^6 cycles, then it was cycled at a higher load level.

The fatigue load per hole that does not lead to failure after 10^6 cycles is greater than $P_{2\%}$ in the case of Jo-bolts and Huck-rivets, while a lower load is found for the bolt and the Bulbed Cherry Lock rivet. Therefore, no relation can be found between $P_{2\%}$ and the fatigue behaviour. The life-time of mechanical fasteners in ca-ep will depend strongly on the shape and the material of the fastener, because the tilting of the fastener introduces high fatigue stresses in the fasteners. So, to select a mechanical fastener for application in ca-ep constructions one needs P_u , $P_{2\%}$ and fatigue data. It has to be emphasized that in all fatigue tests $R = 0.1$ was applied; for $R < 0$ worse results are expected.

3.4 Test method to investigate the behaviour of a row of fasteners.

On account of the results of the single-lap joints the following fasteners were selected for the flap: the protruding head bolt for the heaviest loaded area, for less loaded areas the Jo-bolt or Visu-Lok and further Bulbed Cherry Lock rivets with Ti-backing strips. The Huck-rivet is not used because of the low $P_{2\%}$. The thickness of the laminate of the flap where bolts and Jo-bolts are applied, is 2.8 mm; for these fasteners a diameter of 6.3 mm was chosen in first instance, because the height of the flush head is less than 2.7 mm. The diameter of the Bulbed Cherry Lock rivets is 5.1 mm.

The mechanical behaviour of these fasteners has been tested more thoroughly with the test set-up given in fig. 7: a metal box closed by a ca-ep cover; this cover represents the lower panel of the flap; the ca-ep angles represent the spars of the flap. Due to the loading on the box, the cover will be loaded in shear, which has to be introduced in the ca-ep angles by the rows of fasteners. In this way it is possible to test the characteristic joint in the flap.

In the joint area the laminates consist for about 45% of plies in the 0° -direction (= direction of the row of fasteners), for 45% of plies in the $+45^\circ$ -direction and for about 10% of plies in the 90° -direction. Both static and dynamic tests were carried out on a Trebel testing machine. For the fatigue tests was chosen: $R = 0.1$, $f = 5$ Hz. If a specimen did not fail after 10^6 cycles, then it was cycled at a higher load level, or a residual strength test was carried out.

The relation between the load on the test-box and the shear load in the cover is determined by measuring the strain state of the cover with the aid of strain gauges as a function of the load on the test set-up; such tests have been performed both for an aluminium and for a ca-ep cover. The shear stresses in the cover proved to be nearly constant in the cover; only a difference of about 10% was found in the corners of the cover. Due to the eccentricities in the joint, a bending of the corner occurs (see fig. 7). Due to this effect the fasteners at the corners are heavier loaded than the others. Therefore the ca-ep angles will be stiffened in subsequent tests.

Fig. 7. Test set-up for testing rows of fasteners.

3.5 Test results.

The composition of the tested joints and the test results are given in table 6; the joint consists of the ca-ep cover, the ca-ep angle and in some cases of a Ti-backing strip and/or a Kevlar strip; in this way all the joint configurations of the flap (see fig. 1) are simulated. If flush head fasteners are used, they are countersunk in the cover. In the specimens 1 up to and including 4 flush head Bulbed Cherry Lock-rivets are applied; in specimen 5 protruding head bolts are applied; in the specimens 6 and 7 flush head Jo-bolts are applied.

Spec. no.	fastener type	d (mm)	pitch (mm)	cover t ₁	angle t ₃	Kevlar strip t ₂	Ti-strip t ₄	Type of test	load per fastener (N)	no. of load cycles
1	NAS 1739M6-4	5.11	20	2.55	3.40	-	-	static	4020	-
2	NAS 1739M6-5	5.11	20	2.55	3.40	-	0.8	static	4830	-
3	NAS 1739M6-6	5.11	20	2.75	3.70	2.10	0.8	static	5475	-
4	NAS 1739M6-6	5.11	20	2.75	3.70	2.10	0.8	dyn. P(max): P(max): res.str.	1850 2520 5400	10 ⁶ 800,000 -
5	NAS 674V-6	6.32	27	3.50	3.70	2.10	-	dyn. P(max): P(max): res.str.	3850 5000 9970	10 ⁶ 10 ⁶ -
6	NSA 54204-249-06-1L	6.32	27	2.80	3.70	2.10	0.8	dyn. P(max): P(max):	3170 3850	10 ⁶ 700,000
7	NSA 54204-249-05-1L	6.32	27	2.80	3.70	2.10	-	dyn. P(max): P(max):	3170 3850	10 ⁶ 7000
N.B.: If a specimen did not fail in fatigue after 10 ⁶ cycles, then it was cycled at a higher load level, or a residual strength-test was carried out.							Detail of joint:			

Table 6. Results of tests on metal box with ca-ep cover.

Failure occurred in specimen 1 due to tilting of the fasteners followed by pull through. The allowable load per rivet is greater than in the case of the single-lap joint due to the greater thickness of the ca-ep angles so that tilting of the rivet is better prevented. In the specimens 2 and 3 titanium backing strips are applied; in this case failure occurs due to a crack in the cover through a row of holes. Due to this type of failure, the failure load per fastener is less than the value given in table 4; because of the thicker cover, better results are obtained for specimen 3. The results of the fatigue tests on specimen 4 are in agreement with the expectations: due to a greater plate thickness under the formed head, the tilting of the rivets is prevented in some degree, so that better fatigue results are obtained than with the lap joints. The failure in the residual strength test is due to failure of the rivets. These results and the results of the lap joint tests led to the conclusion that Bulbed Cherry Lock-rivets can be used in the flap in those areas where the load per rivet is less than or equal to 2000 N at daily load; so, no failure through the holes has to be expected at design ultimate load.

The results of the fatigue tests on the bolts with the aid of specimen 5 were satisfactory. In the residual strength test the laminate of one of the angles failed. The results for the Jo-bolts (specimens 6 and 7) are disappointing; the allowable loads on these fasteners with a diameter of 6.32 mm are not greater than those on the 4.8 mm Jo-bolts. Failure is caused by serious tilting of the bolts. This will probably be due to the fact that the height of the flush head is 2.7 mm; so, the height of the cylindrical part of the countersunk hole is only 0.1 mm. Due to these results it was decided to apply in the flap only flush head Jo-bolts with a diameter of 4.8 mm; the behaviour of these fasteners will be investigated with the aid of the test set-up treated here.

3.6 Conclusions.

Generally only expensive mechanical fasteners are appropriate for application in ca-ep constructions due to the requirement that the material of the fastener should not corrode when it is in contact with carbon and due to the restriction that only low expansion shank rivets should be applied. The fastener to be used in ca-ep must be formed in such a way that tilting due to loading, is prevented as much as possible; a large tilt can be due to a bad shape of the formed head or to an insufficient cylindrical part of a countersunk hole.

To select a mechanical fastener for a joint in ca-ep, as well P_u , $P_{2\%}$ as fatigue data are needed. The load at which 2% permanent deformation of the holes occurs, has to be determined by tests at a low load-velocity because of creep in the joint.

The following effects will have to be investigated more thoroughly:

- does the lateral constraint in the ca-ep decrease due to stress-relaxation?
- are the ranges of grip-length that have been determined for joints in metals, also applicable for joints in ca-ep?
- what is the influence of environmental effects?
- can the results of lap-joint tests be used to predict the behaviour of a joint consisting of a row of fasteners loaded in shear? In the investigations treated in this paper, no attention was paid to this question, because all the tests were performed to support the development of the flap.

4 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The author wishes to acknowledge the help of G.J. Fonk, who developed the method to test a row of fasteners loaded in shear, and of P. Diederer, W. Hooger-vorst and A. v. Wieringen for testing.

REFERENCES

1. MACHIELSE, L., SLAGER, D., VERNOOY, C.: Development, production, calculation and testing of a carbon/Kevlar fibre reinforced flap; to be published in proceedings ICCM III.
2. WEBB, E.L.: Riveting and bolting in carbon fibre composite. Proceedings of the symposium on jointing in fibre reinforced plastics, 4/5 september 1978; pp.28-41.
3. NEVADUNSKY, J.J., LUCAS, J.J., SALKIND, M.J.: Early fatigue damage detection in composite materials. J.Composite Materials, Vol.9, 1975, pp. 394-408.
4. BROUTMAN, L.J, SAHU, S.: Progressive damage of a glass reinforced plastic during fatigue. 24th Annual Technical Conference SPI, 1969, section 11-D.
5. GRIMES, G.C.: Structural design significance of tension-tension fatigue data on composites; ASTM STP 617, 1977, pp. 106-120.
6. OCH, F.: Schädigungsgrenzen bei Faserverbundstrukturen. DGLR-Nr. 76-228.
7. PARVIZI, A., GARRETT, K.W., BAILY, J.E.: Constrained cracking in glass fibre reinforced epoxy cross-ply laminates. J. of Materials Science, Vol. 13, 1978, pp. 195-201.
8. COLLINGS, T.A.: The strength of bolted joints in multi-directional cfrp laminates. Composites, Jan. 1977, pp. 43-56.
9. HART-SMITH, L.J.: Bolted joints in graphite-epoxy composites. NASA-CR-144899.
10. STOCKDALE, J.H., MATTHEWS, F.L.: The effect of clamping pressure on bolt bearing loads in glass fibre reinforced plastics. Composites, Jan. 1976, pp. 34-39